

Coastal Proximity and the ‘Shared Risk Identity’: Mapping Willingness to Pay for Flood Protection in Mozambique

Jacob L. Macdonald^{*1}, Stefan Leeffers^{†2}, Caroline Mieke³,
Patricia Caetano⁴ and Pedro C. Vicente^{‡3}

¹University of Sheffield – School of Geography and Planning

²University College London – Dept. of Risk and Disaster Reduction

³Nova School of Business and Economics

⁴University of Southern California – Dept. of Economics

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Summary

Data scarcity often hinders granular spatial analysis of urban climate adaptation in the Global South. This study utilises a geographically explicit survey of 2,445 households in Quelimane, Mozambique, to explore determinants of willingness to pay for flood mitigation. Integrating primary survey data with GIS layers (Google Open Buildings, elevation), we employ Global and Local Moran’s I to identify spatial regimes of adaptation behaviour. Findings reveal significant clustering (Global Moran’s I = 0.1832), particularly in coastal, mangrove-adjacent and low-elevation areas. Coastal residents exhibit a "shared risk identity," where environmental exposure yields collective expectations, suggesting that policies must transition toward spatially tailored interventions.

KEYWORDS: Willingness to Pay, Flood Mitigation, Spatial Clustering, Climate Adaptation

1. Introduction

Residential location preferences and related behaviours in urban areas are heavily mediated by access to local amenities and infrastructure, proximity to employment hubs and essential services, and exposure to environmental hazards and risks (Adelekan and Asiyani, 2016; Jongman, 2018; Berndtsson et al., 2019). In semi-urbanised developing cities of the Global South, location is particularly important due to the lack of public transport option and the use of informal land tenure systems. The way in which individuals react to environmental hazards like regular flooding is a complex calculation of risk, capacity, cost and location.

We collect a novel survey dataset from Quelimane, Mozambique, exploring how residents engage with flood hazards around their neighbourhood. Despite the increasing prevalence of extreme weather events, recently evidenced through the experiences of events like Cyclones Idai (2019) and Freddy

* j.macdonald@sheffield.ac.uk

† s.leeffers@ucl.ac.uk

‡ pedro.vicente@novasbe.pt

(2023), data scarcity in the global south often prevents granular analysis of how residents value localised flood mitigation strategies and interventions. We complement residential location and contexts with a series of geospatial land use and environmental data, bridging the gap between advanced geospatial analytics and individual's willingness' to pay.

2. Data and Study Region

2.1. Quelimane, Mozambique

Quelimane is the capital of the Zambezia province and situated inland along the *Cuacua River* estuary, known by early explorers as the *Rio dos Bons Sinais*, and located approximately 20 km inland from the coast and the Mozambique Channel. The urban area has a population of around 349,842 (Instituto Nacional de Estatística, 2019). Its tidal river setting and proximity to a channel notorious for cyclonic activity subject the city to drastic seasonal fluctuations in water levels. While residents and traders have historically adapted to these changes over time, increasing frequency and intensity of these tropical storms continue to place unprecedented strain on coastal cities and infrastructure (Fitchett and Grab, 2014). The geography and location of Quelimane exacerbate this challenge. The topography of the city is flat with little variation, lying primarily at sea level and at the confluence of various waterways.

Figure 1 Quelimane, Mozambique

2.2. Data Collection

We collect and use both primary and secondary data with locational attributes from a variety of sources. Secondary data from the WorldPop (WorldPop, 2023), Humanitarian OSM (OpenStreetMap contributors, 2024) and Google Building Footprints (Sirko et al., 2021) provided a benchmark overview of the built and natural environment of the area prior to (and informing our) primary data collection.

Our sampling is done at the administrative block level, which are organised among larger administrative areas (*Postos*). There is a total of seven *postos* and 557 city blocks. We selected four random households within each city block using open-source building data (Sirko et al., 2021). The block chief was also included for surveying, for a total target of five observations per block. The random locations were divided into male and female respondents to enable a gender-balanced household sample.

The resulting dataset comprises 2,445 observations. The average age of respondents is 41.15 (SD = 14.83), and about 55% (N = 1,345) have a household income less than 6,000 MT (approximately £70 per month). The sample is characterised by high educational engagement, with over 93% of participants having accessed formal schooling, mostly completed or partially completed primary and secondary schooling. The most common occupations were independent workers (39%; N = 957) or farming and fishing (8.8%; N = 216).

Table 1.A Categorical Frequency WTP and Repair Costs

WTP (Categorical)		Repairs (Categorical)	
0 MT	542 (23%)	0 MT	40 (3.6%)
< 500 MT	700 (29%)	< 500 MT	35 (3.1%)
500 - 999 MT	422 (18%)	500 - 999 MT	23 (2.1%)
1,000 - 1,499 MT	279 (12%)	1,000 - 1,499 MT	37 (3.3%)
1,500 - 1,999 MT	90 (3.8%)	1,500 - 1,999 MT	45 (4.0%)
2,000 - 4,999 MT	167 (7.0%)	2,000 - 4,999 MT	190 (17%)
5,000 - 9,999 MT	99 (4.1%)	5,000 - 9,999 MT	219 (20%)
10,000 - 19,999 MT	55 (2.3%)	10,000 - 19,999 MT	218 (20%)
20,000 - 49,999 MT	25 (1.0%)	20,000 - 49,999 MT	197 (18%)
> 50,000 MT	20 (0.8%)	> 50,000 MT	113 (10%)
<i>NA's</i>	46	<i>NA's</i>	1,328
Numeric Rank 1-10	3.06 (2.03)	Numeric Rank 1-10	7.05 (2.20)
<i>NA's</i>	46	<i>NA's</i>	1,328

Notes: Mean (SD); n (%) N = 2,445

The primary household-level surveys were designed to capture a multi-dimensional view of urban vulnerability, combining objective socio-economic metrics with subjective assessments of risk and financial agency. Residents were asked about their willingness to pay (WTP) for disaster insurance, capturing the value they would purchase insurance at to cover damages and loss from flooding disaster (as a categorical value). They were also asked about their willingness to contribute towards a localised fund for collective flood infrastructure at the block level (continuous value), the count of recent flood experiences, and the (categorical) value of repairs needed to compensate for the most recent cyclone event, Freddy, if they were impacted.

Table 1.B Outcome Mean Values by Posto

	Overall <i>N</i> = 2,445	Posto 1 <i>N</i> = 390	Posto 2 <i>N</i> = 355	Posto 3 <i>N</i> = 505	Posto 4 <i>N</i> = 770	Posto 6 <i>N</i> = 65	Posto 7 <i>N</i> = 360
WTP (Rank)	3.06 (2.03)	2.88 (1.94)	3.66 (2.40)	2.93 (2.00)	3.12 (2.05)	2.31 (1.62)	2.83 (1.58)
<i>NA</i> 's	46	16	4	10	15	0	1
Flood Contributions	288.82 (629.22)	353.02 (646.72)	277.52 (637.23)	224.96 (363.85)	297.08 (589.68)	348.42 (1,850.56)	291.14 (528.38)
<i>NA</i> 's	41	5	2	10	23	0	1
Flood Count	2.04 (2.90)	1.53 (2.17)	2.57 (4.35)	2.37 (3.02)	2.00 (2.56)	3.23 (4.11)	1.45 (1.51)
<i>NA</i> 's	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Repairs (Rank)	7.05 (2.20)	7.30 (1.98)	7.21 (2.21)	6.79 (2.58)	7.00 (2.28)	7.10 (1.37)	7.09 (1.69)
<i>NA</i> 's	1,328	231	165	261	445	35	191

Notes: Mean (Standard Deviation); Posto 5 omitted due to uninhabited rural nature.

3. Methods

This work is an exploratory spatial analysis looking at patterns in willingness to pay for localised flood risk infrastructure. The location within the city, topography and proximity to coastline all provide unequal exposure and risks when it comes to water hazards. We collect the underlying location information from respondents so that we can exploit the geographic dimensions of our data and run some spatial data analytics.

We calculate a series of Moran I statistics (Moran, 1950) across different measures to determine whether there is any spatial clustering in respondent behaviour – that is, whether individuals with higher willingness to pay (for e.g.) tend to be located near others with higher willingness to pay. We calculate this global estimate of spatial autocorrelation for measures of individual willingness to pay, hypothetical flood contribution, flood count (occurrences) and the amount of damage from the most recent cyclone.

Here we are estimating a variable's correlation with the neighbouring values of itself, providing an overall indicator of how strongly clustered values are over space. From this, we can comment on whether neighbourhood similarities emerge in how much residents are willing to pay for local flood mitigation. The Moran statistic is given by the formula:

$$I = \left[\frac{N}{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \right] \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} (x_i - \bar{x}) (x_j - \bar{x})}{\sum_{i=1}^N w_{ij} (x_i - \bar{x})} \quad (1)$$

Here, the autocorrelation between a variable x with N observations is calculated. One of the core aspects of this calculation, which differentiates it from a traditional correlation, is the use of a $N \times N$ spatial weight matrix made up of elements w_{ij} which measures the strength of proximity between observation x_i and x_j . We measure that here by using the inverse Euclidean distance. That is, the strength of each pair-wise relationship over space is inversely proportional to how close observations are to each other, and the x values are weighted proportionately.

We do two things to explore localised variations in the dataset and depart from the global estimates. Firstly, we split the dataset into different location-based subsets, which allows us to estimate and compare the values and strength of the relationship for our willingness to pay across different key areas of the city. Using the spatial nature of the data, we explore how factors such as proximity to the coast or living in low-lying areas might yield different patterns and strengths in willingness to pay.

While the Global Moran I provides a single summary statistic to determine if the overall spatial distribution of the data is clustered, dispersed, or random, it can mask local patterns and heterogeneity across the city. We thus further estimate Local Indicators of Spatial Association (LISA) using the Local Moran I statistic (Anselin, 1995). The formula used for the LISA calculation is as follows:

$$I_i = \left[\frac{N-1}{\sum_{j=1}^N (x_j - \bar{x})^2} \right] (x_i - \bar{x}) \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} (x_j - \bar{x}) \quad (2)$$

Unlike global measures of autocorrelation, the LISA exploration allows us to pinpoint specific ‘hot spots’ (high values surrounded by high values) and ‘cold spots’ (low values surrounded by low values) of the outcomes of interest. This approach is key for identifying whether community-led mitigation efforts are spatially clustered in specific locations or if they are fragmented across the city’s complex topography. We use this as an exploratory analysis to see where spatial heterogeneity might exist.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 2 Moran I Clustering of Outcome Variables

	WTP (Rank)	Flood Contribution	Flood Count	Repairs (Rank)
	Mor. I (Mean)	Mor. I (Mean)	Mor. I (Mean)	Mor. I (Mean)
Global Moran I	0.1832^{***} (3.06)	0.0379^{***} (288.82)	0.1917^{***} (2.04)	0.2410^{***} (7.05)
Near the Coastline	0.2299 ^{***} (3.00)	0.038 ^{**} (316.32)	0.225 ^{***} (1.68)	0.1621 ^{***} (7.18)
Not near the Coastline	0.1341 ^{***} (3.12)	0.0276 ^{**} (261.49)	0.1455 ^{***} (2.40)	0.2964 ^{***} (6.93)
Mangrove Adjacent	0.2666 ^{***} (2.65)	0.0314 (338.75)	0.1783 ^{***} (2.10)	0.1219 ^{***} (7.11)
Not near Mangrove	0.1598 ^{***} (3.13)	0.0392 ^{***} (279.56)	0.1938 ^{***} (2.03)	0.2545 ^{***} (7.03)
Low Population Dens	0.2066 ^{***} (2.99)	0.0386 ^{**} (273.77)	0.2031 ^{***} (2.48)	0.2092 ^{***} (7.15)
High Population Dens	0.1732 ^{***} (3.11)	0.0369 ^{**} (303.14)	0.1346 ^{***} (1.61)	0.2717 ^{***} (6.93)
Low Elevation	0.1888 ^{***} (2.89)	0.0359 ^{**} (294.7)	0.1483 ^{***} (1.92)	0.217 ^{***} (7.09)
High Elevation	0.1654 ^{***} (3.26)	0.0392 ^{**} (282.53)	0.2576 ^{***} (2.16)	0.278 ^{***} (6.99)

Notes: Significance * 10% Level; ** 5% Level; *** 1% Level

Results show that flooding preferences and WTP can be highly localized. The global Moran I estimate of 0.1832 indicates moderate global clustering, with significant local hotspots emerge in areas closer to the coastline and mangrove plantations. We see similar, but weaker, clustering from flooding contributions. As expected, similar clustering is seen in the self-reported number of flooding events and the repairs needed for recent events across the city.

Table 2 shows estimate for the Moran I for various subsets of the survey, conditional on location. We use geospatial data and variables to subset the survey responses according to different urban characteristics — using median values to split the data into high and low partitions (except for mangrove adjacency, which is defined as being in a block bordering mangroves). The Moran I spatial clustering value is accompanied by the average value for the willingness to pay variable within each subset and can show us both where and whether we might have values which cluster together, and what the ultimate average value within those areas are.

Figure 2 visualises these impacts for the WTP and reported flood counts. We map out the value of responses over space and use the LISA estimates to create buffer polygons to highlight and identify the areas where there is significant (hot spot) clustering over space.

Figure 2 Spatial Distribution of Outcomes and Significant Local Hot Spot Clusters

Some interesting spatial patterns emerge, suggesting the importance of considering location and context in flood management preferences. While we may observe relatively strong similarities in how people behave across different spaces — that is, specific neighbourhoods having similar willingness to pay for flood defence, this may vary in terms of the magnitude of whether individuals are willing to contribute

towards flood mitigation. For example, while there is relatively stronger clustering of values for those respondents closer to the coastline, the overall willingness to pay between those near the coastline and those who are not is similar. For respondents who are nearer to mangrove forests, we see a similar willingness to pay, but overall, it is less in magnitude on average compared to those who are not. Interestingly, while residents near the coastline show similar average WTP to those inland, their behaviour is more strongly clustered. This suggests that coastal proximity creates a ‘shared risk identity’ that stabilizes expectations of collective contribution.

By spatially anchoring behavioural data, we demonstrate that location can be a statistically significant driver of localised community-based climate adaptation behaviour. These results suggest that flood management policies should be tailored to specific spatial regimes within the city, rather than applying a uniform strategy. Future research will focus on making these geospatial layers openly available to support local infrastructure planning and disaster response.

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Biographies

Jacob L. Macdonald is a Lecturer in GIS and Spatial Analysis at the University of Sheffield. His research applies urban and environmental economics and data science to explore neighbourhood dynamics. He focuses on leveraging big, geographic data and quantitative methods to understand the spillovers of urban amenities and the built environment.

Stefan Leeffers is a Lecturer in Crises and Disaster Risk Finance at University College London's Institute for Risk and Disaster Reduction. A development economist, his research focuses on disaster risk management and political economy in low- and middle-income countries, using impact evaluations to identify strategies that build community resilience.

Caroline Mieke is a Researcher at NOVAFRICA, Nova School of Business and Economics, and holds a PhD from KU Leuven. Specializing in development and agricultural economics, her research utilizes randomized field experiments to examine information asymmetries, technology adoption, and community resilience in the face of poverty and climate change.

Patrícia Caetano is a PhD student in Economics at the University of Southern California (USC). Her research interests centre on applying economic analysis to global challenges, including poverty, health, and climate change. She has extensive experience coordinating field experiments and randomized controlled trials focused on migration and climate risks.

Pedro C. Vicente is a Professor of Economics at Nova School of Business and Economics and the Scientific Director of NOVAFRICA. His research specializes in development economics and political economy, with a particular focus on Africa. He has led numerous field experiments on mobile money, education, and governance.